

Policy Cloud
Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

Project Number: 870675

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2020

Duration: 36 months

D6.9 INTEGRATION OF RESULTS: POLICYCLOUD COMPLETE ENVIRONMENT M36

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/12/2022 (M36)
Actual Submission Date	21/12/2022
Work Package	WP6, Use Case Adaptation, Integration & Experimentation
Task	T6.1 Integration
Type	Demonstrator
Approval Status	
Version	V2.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.32

Abstract: This document contains complementary material for the PolicyCLOUD installation environment. It includes detailed instructions regarding the final installation and integration of the components as well as an analysis of the cloud environment that the platform is hosted.

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PolicyCloud has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870675.

Versioning and Contribution History

Version	Date	Reason	Author
1.1	23/11/2022	Update ToC	ICCS
1.2	11/12/2022	Update integration content	ICCS
1.3	15/12/2022	Update content from the components	All Partners
1.4	15/12/2022	Final refinements	ICCS
1.5	18/12/2022	First Review	IBM
1.6	20/12/2022	Second Review	LXS
1.7	21/12/2022	Quality Check	UPRC
2.0	21/12/2022	Submitted version	Atos

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
DAA	Data Acquisition and Analytics
DORA	DevOps Research and Assessment
EBPM	Evidence Based Policy Making
EC	European Commission
ELSA	Entity-Level Sentiment Analysis
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IM	Incentives Management
JDBC	Java Database Connectivity
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PME	Policy Model Editor
SLA	Service Level Agreement
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

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Executive Summary

This deliverable has been released in December 2022, at M36 of the project, and its main objective is to specify the **final** integration results between the PolicyCLOUD components.

This deliverable will follow the methodology of D6.2 and D6.8 that were respectively submitted in M12 (December 2020) and M24 (December 2021) which have two main pillars:

1. Define common practices for integration and validation of the outcomes of the project
2. Detail the cloud environment the project will make use of to demonstrate the results

Regarding the former, GitLab will be the base code repository for the project, where the project already owns an organizational account. Over GitLab [1], the trunk-based development branching policy has been applied, as we considered it the most suitable policy given the project characteristics. Also, GitLab's issue reporting tool has been adopted, as it is fully integrated with GitLab's features. The test bed to support the demonstrators has been deployed over EGI's (EGI) infrastructure where flexibility is one of the critical features.

This deliverable abstractly incorporates all the changes and implementations that WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 had made during the second year of the project. More details about the components and the actual implementation can be found in the related WP deliverables [7] [8] [9].

In detail, the schemas of the data have been finalized so the standard version that we defined initiated the data import to the repository of PolicyCLOUD. Moreover, the infrastructure (IaaS) and the platform deployment (PaaS/ Serverless) have been restructured and reshaped based on the latest needs of the components. EGI deployed the new flavour of PolicyCLOUD to the Openstack Infrastructure and IBM made the proper changes to the Openwhisk middleware for the serverless and other services. The related WP deliverables highlight detailed information and instructions for each component change that in total orchestrate the PolicyCLOUD engine.

1 Introduction

In the following section the overall Architecture that was presented in D2.6 Conceptual Model & Reference Architecture M18 (the revised version) [7] is decomposed and analyzed. The main goal is to identify **HOW** each component can be deployed, **WHERE** it can be instantiated and **WHAT** are the **API interfaces** that are offered. Also, it analyzes the technical constraints for the cloud environment and the minimum requirements necessary for the full deployment.

FIGURE 1 - OVERALL CORE COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE (UPDATED)

2 Components

In the following section a description of the component and a reference to the source code is provided.

2.1 Data Acquisition

FIGURE 2 - DATA ACQUISITION LAYER

2.1.1 Cloud Gateways & APIs for Efficient Data Utilization

The Cloud Gateway and API component enhances the abilities and services offered by a unified Gateway to move streaming and batch data from data owners into PolicyCLOUD data management layer, which supports access to both SQL and NoSQL data stores and public and private data. On top of this, the main goal of this component is to handle each request by invoking the appropriate microservices and aggregating the results. Hence, it enhances the design of resources and structure, add dynamic routing parameters, and develop custom authorizations logic. PolicyCLOUD's Cloud Gateway and API component is scalable, highly available and fault tolerant, also it shares state without compromising performance.

In a microservices environment the running instances of services dynamically change location inside networks. In order for client or services to be able to make requests to a service it must use a service-discovery mechanism. As introduced in D3.8, the Cloud Gateways and APIs component rely on the utilization of a unified set of microservices. To this end, Cloud Gateways & APIs component consists of two main sub-components with internal microservices implemented on them. The overall implementation has been based on the utilization of MoleculerJS, as it provides a built-in module to handle service discovery and registry. The underlying concept of service discovery is the exchange of heartbeats packets between the registry and the available nodes, to list the working services. If a node fails to broadcast a heartbeat is not used to serve requests made for this particular service. The initial design of these two specific sub-components, that can be used either for fetching data from an external file or from a social media platform like Twitter, includes complete workflows and pipelines for pushing data into the PolicyCLOUD platform. These sub-components have been integrated with each other and project's authentication mechanism (both ABAC and KeyCloak) controls access to them.

In addition during the past year, additional parameters have been added to the registration APIs (both for datasets and analytic functions) to support the legal requirements. For details, please refer the DAA section of D4.5 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Design and Open Specification 3 [9].

2.1.1.1 TWITTER CONNECTOR COMPONENT

FIGURE 3 - TWITTER CONNECTOR COMPONENT

The Twitter Connector is a component of the Cloud Gateway, providing access to Twitter data to the Gateway's clients without the need to directly connect to Twitter API. It has been implemented in NodeJS utilizing the twitter-v2 npm package⁷. Furthermore, Twitter is launching the API v2, an improved version which promises to provide a better developer experience by giving access to a wide variety of data sources and tools. Twitter ensures the quality of its data by applying spam filters, access to all results of a query and not only to a partition of results, user-friendly and simplified JSON objects, shorter URLs and OpenAPI specification to test endpoints and watch for any change. One of the major limitations of data collection using the Twitter API is that the client machine will always try to keep up with the data stream otherwise the stream just disconnects. Hence, in order to overcome this limitation, this component integrates also with Kafka [10] event streaming platform, so raw Twitter data can be processed without worrying about the stream getting disconnected.

Finally, this specific subcomponent has two (2) basic functionalities/microservices incorporated in each implementation, as also depicted in Figure 3.

- **Twitter API:** for searching and filtering tweets by utilizing the Search Tweets endpoints of the Twitter API v2, and by this microservice Cloud Gateway's users have access to the most recent

tweets¹. The Twitter Connector sub-component provides a REST application interface following the OpenAPI specification in order to be easier for the end user to discover the capabilities of the component and to provide well-structured documentation for each of the component's services. The filters that can be applied include:

- Keyword search
- The start and end time parameters to limit tweet results to a specific period of time
- Max number of tweets in order to limit the results returned
- **Twitter Stream API:** to stream tweets for a specific period of time by utilizing the Filtered Stream endpoints and by which the Cloud Gateways component allow users to capture tweets in real-time related to a specific topic for a pre-selected time window². The available parameters for the endpoint are including:
 - Keyword
 - Duration (milliseconds): The duration parameter specifies the duration of the stream capturing process. There is a max-duration limit, in order to ensure gateway's users are not abusing the service and also Twitter's rate limits policy³.

2.1.1.2 INTERIM REPOSITORY CONNECTOR COMPONENT

The Interim Repository Connector sub-component is responsible for the fetching of batch data into the overall PolicyCLOUD platform. This sub-component incorporates several microservices, such as RAND, Sofia and GTD microservices, each one of them addressing a different use case scenario of the project. In addition, it also provides a REST application interface following the OpenAPI specification in order to be easier for the end user to discover the capabilities of the component and to provide well-structured documentation for each of the component's services.

¹ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/search/api-reference/get-tweets-search-recent>

² <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/filtered-stream/introduction>

³ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/rate-limits>

FIGURE 4 - INTERIM REPOSITORY CONNECTOR COMPONENT

- These microservices integrate with the project’s Interim Repository to fetch the needed datasets for each specific scenario. While some of them also offer the ability to the end user to indicate the exact dataset to be fetched by placing the name of the dataset as a parameter in the exposed endpoint.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

For all the above-mentioned subcomponents the source code and an installation manual are available on the following repository <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cloudgatewayv2>. The installation instructions and project requirements are firmly described inside the project’s README.md file <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cloudgatewayv2/-/blob/master/README.md>.

2.2 Data Analytics

FIGURE 5 - DATA ANALYTICS LAYER

2.2.1 The Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA)

This Layer is the central layer of PolicyCLOUD, between the cloud infrastructure and the Policy layers. This layer provides the functionality for ingesting data coming from various sources while applying filtering and initial analytics, preparing it for deeper analytics on longer term storage (DB, object storage).

2.2.2 DAA API Gateway

The DAA API Gateway is responsible for the orchestration and integration of all the components of the DAA layer (analytic functions, data sources, data repository) as well as providing the external interface for the layer’s exploiters – analytic owners, data source owners, and the Policy layer (through which the end user apply desired analytics). Its roles include forming the proper setup of the registered analytic functions and data sources to ensure the correct data ingest process (applying the required ingest-time analytics/transformation – in both Ingest-now and Streaming modes) and applying the requested analytics on the requested data source. The DAA API Gateway is implemented as a set of serverless functions (in the OpenWhisk [3] cluster), where the state is managed both on the OpenWhisk itself (e.g. analytic functions’ metadata) and the database.

The methods that are exposed are:

- ANALYTIC FUNCTION REGISTRATION
- DATA SOURCE REGISTRATION
- LIST REGISTERED FUNCTIONS
- LIST REGISTERED DATA SOURCES
- APPLY FUNCTION
- GET JOB STATUS

Software prototype code can be found on the PolicyCLOUD’s github which is accessible to the members of the consortium and includes code to deploy in OpenWhisk.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/oshrit/daa>

The setup details for the DAA prototype environment are detailed in “D4.6 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 3”, section 3.2.1 DAA API Gateway.

The sole notable change in this past year was the addition of the new “existing” data source type which permits to “ingest” a dataset that is already in the PolicyCLOUD environment datastore (the LeanXcale database) without having been registered through the DAA. This may occur for instance when a dataset is directly ingested from another pipeline like AWS blue within the database. This is the use case that triggered addition of this new data source, but many others use cases are potentially relevant. It should be also noticed that ingest analytics may be applied (exactly the same as for any other data source type) when ingesting an “existing” dataset. This change has occurred after the submission of D4.5 [9] but has been reported in D4.6 [11] at section 2.1.1

2.2.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

In the context of Situational Knowledge Acquisition and Analysis, the **SKA-EDA component** has been provided for the exploration of datasets based on descriptive analysis conducted by data visualization. This is the last prototype developed in the task and it includes the following functionalities (citing D4.6 deliverable):

- Frequency distribution of one or two variables across multiple categories. Representing the number of apparitions of one (or more) value/category corresponding to observable variable (s) in a specific dataset. The JSON results has (horizontal) bar chart as main visualization chart.
- Geographical Distribution. Representing the list of observations that happen in concretes values of a geographical-based variable. The JSON results has “heat map” as main visualization chart.
- Accumulation of one variable across multiple categories. This distribution provides the accumulated value (sum the value of a specific numeric variable) across several categories. The results are portrayed as a bar chart.
- Temporal Evolution: List of values of a specific numeric variable across several categories

This component oversees providing exploratory analysis over different datasets, in particular is able to process the following datasets:

- 6 datasets coming from Sofia Municipality’s Contact Centre CallSofia (mobile application, 24/7 phone contact centre, and web channel) which belong to the Use case 3 (Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis),
- GTD data base which belongs to Use case 1 (Participatory policies against Radicalization).
- Sales prices dataset belongs to Use case 2 (Intelligent policies for agri-food industry).

This component is fully integrated in the PolicyCLOUD framework and with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components: the DAA API Gateway developed in the context of WP4, available as an OpenWhisk function, the PolicyCLOUD storage for feeding data and storing the results and the PDT for its invocation.

On the other hand, it has integrated a new component in PolicyCLOUD system for the final release. This is **SKA-TSF component** in charge of applying stochastic-based techniques for forecasting univariate time series datasets. This is the last prototype developed in the task and it includes the following functionalities D4.6 [11]:

- **Training Service:** A process for fitting a specific model for a specific training dataset and based on a pre-determine hyperparameters. In summary, this process retrieves a (training) dataset, based on the name passed as input parameter, performs the needed transformations and finally configures and fitting a particular model with concrete hyper-parameters
- **Predicting Service:** Based on a selected trained model, given the name/id as parameter, the process is able to return predicted values (in the form of a json file) for a horizon forecast passed as input. It's worth mentioning that the predicting process will throw reliable outcomes for the future within the next 6 months from the last period (in our case, last day) of the trained dataset used in the selected model. Therefore, it is up to the user the responsibility of keeping the model freshly re-trained with recent data for obtaining optimal results close to recent days.

This component oversees providing time series forecasting for a particular dataset:

- 1 dataset coming from Sofia Municipality's Contact Centre CallSofia (mobile application, 24/7 phone contact centre, and web channel) which belong to the Use case 3 (Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis), in particular is Road Infrastructure dataset.

This component is fully integrated in the PolicyCLOUD framework and with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components: the DAA API Gateway developed in the context of WP4, available as an OpenWhisk function, the PolicyCLOUD storage for feeding data and storing the results and the PDT for its invocation

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

Similarly to the Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis Component, all the information related to this component is written in the latest version of D4.6 along with all the details about the baseline technologies and tools used, analytics performed, the description of the parameters that are used as input to execute it, and the outputs that will be generated in the execution.

All the source code is available at the project's git:

- <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/maria.sanguino/exploratoryanalysis>.
- <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/maria.sanguino/timeseriesforecasting>

2.2.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis Component

The latest version of this component is based on an entity-level sentiment analysis (ELSA) approach [13] aiming at identifying the sentiment identified in a text regarding a set of elements identified in that text. This improved version will support the project use cases by aggregating and providing the corresponding sentiment scores for identified and extracted entities in Tweets.

In order to provide the two functionalities described, two services are provided:

- A service that calculates the sentiment scores (as a numeric value from 0, meaning negative sentiment, to 1, meaning positive sentiment) of the identified entities in a given text. This service requires as input both the definition of the entities to analyse as well as the text where those entities have been mentioned.
- A service that aggregates the sentiment scores of the identified entities both temporal and geographically to ease its visualization. This service requires connection details to the database where the sentiment data is stored as well as a time window definition to delimit the mentions to analyse. Also, a parameter to define the temporal granularity to perform the aggregation of the sentiment should be provided.

This component is fully integrated in the PolicyCLOUD framework and with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components: the DAA API Gateway developed in the context of WP4, available as an OpenWhisk function and the PDT for its invocation.

All the information related to this component is written in “D4.6 REUSABLE MODEL & ANALYTICAL TOOLS: SOFTWARE PROTOTYPE 3” along with all the details about the baseline technologies and tools used.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

All the resources needed for the sentiment analysis, are available at the project’s git: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/jorge.montero/sentimentanalysis>

2.2.5 Trend analysis component

The Trend Analysis component has been developed in order to provide enriched information regarding the identified entities in social media interactions. This enriched information is based on a modelling of the different use cases where it is applied provided (as an ontology or taxonomy) by their responsible contact. By means of using this modelling, different aggregations can be performed taking into account conceptual factors (i.e., focus on certain sets of entities related with another one or focus on entities of a given type).

This Trend analysis component has been designed to provide the following services:

- Conceptualizer: This service receives a given text or social media interaction (i.e. tweets) along with the different entities that have been identified in that text. The service will enrich the input data in two ways: 1) calling the sentiment analysis component with the entities identified in the text and 2) adding information of those entities that are related to the mentioned ones in the text. As a result, all this data will be stored in a database for its further processing in other analytics.
- Tag cloud: this service will filter all the mentions identified in the social media interactions given a time window. These mentions will be returned with an indicator of their presence in social media along with related entities. Different criteria can be selected to choose the relations

between the entities returned (e.g., entities of a given type, entities linked with a given entity, etc.).

- Bursty analysis: this service, given two time windows, throws information on those entities with the highest increase or decrease of mentions in social media during those time windows provided, in order to identify trends in terms based on social media interactions.

This component is fully integrated in the PolicyCLOUD framework and with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components: the DAA API Gateway developed in the context of WP4, available as an OpenWhisk function and the PDT for its invocation.

All the information related to this component is written in “D4.6 REUSABLE MODEL & ANALYTICAL TOOLS: SOFTWARE PROTOTYPE 3” along with all the details about the baseline technologies and tools used.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

Regarding the Trend analysis component, all the required elements for its functioning can be found at the project’s git: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/maria.sanguino/trendanalysis/>

2.2.6 Social Dynamics

The Social Dynamics component of PolicyCLOUD is referred to as Politika. It is an interactive, web-based meta-simulation framework for policy analysis and design. It can be used either as a stand-alone component or as an integrated tool with the PolicyCloud platform through a REST API. The version of the Politika server that supports the REST API runs at epinoetic.org:5000 and accepts requests from PolicyCLOUD. Section 2.5.1. of deliverable D4.6 describes this component and its integration to PoliciCLOUD in detail.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

The source code for the Social Dynamics component that implements the Rest API for integration with the PolicyCloud environment resides in: http://epinoetic.org/Assets/politika_api.zip.

The programmer’s manual for the Politika system resides in: <http://epinoetic.org/Assets/doc.zip>.

Installation instructions reside in: <http://epinoetic.org/Assets/install.txt>.

2.2.7 Operational Data Repository

FIGURE 6 - MAIN REPOSITORY (ULTRASCALABLE OPERATIONAL DATABASE)

Mapping and creating interoperable data depend on providing semantic and syntactic interoperability across diverse systems, data sources and datasets. To this end, PolicyCLOUD's Enhanced Interoperability Component aims to enhance interoperability into PolicyCLOUD project based on data-driven design by the utilization of linked data technologies, and standards-based ontologies and vocabularies, coupled with the use of powerful tasks from the domain of Natural Language Processing (NLP), in order to improve both semantic and syntactic interoperability of data and datasets. To this end, the Enhanced Interoperability Component consists of several methods, and sub-tasks, which are further separated into different layers of the overall proposed pipeline. The initial design of these layers, that integrate Semantic Web technologies with Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies and tasks, includes complete workflows and pipelines for annotating cleaned data, which are sent to the Enhanced Interoperability Component from the Data Cleaning Component. The latter has resulted into the introduction of the SemAI hybrid mechanism in the context of the Enhanced Interoperability component. This mechanism can be applied in a wider range of various scenarios and heterogeneous data sources due to its generalized and schema-agnostic nature. To this end, its utilization has a major impact on the successful aggregation, analysis, and exploitation of data across the whole policy making life cycle within the PolicyCLOUD platform.

Hence, several subtasks and functionalities have been introduced and utilized so far in this component and in the context of its third prototype. More specifically, as also analyzed thoroughly in D4.6 [11], the SemAI mechanism incorporates two main subcomponents, the Linguistic & Semantic Analysis with NLP (1st sub-component) and the Ontology Mapping (2nd sub-component). Furthermore, the abovementioned subcomponents utilize different subtasks from the fields of NLP and Semantic Web, such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), JSON URI annotation, Topic Modeling, and Ontology Mapping.

Moreover, under the scope of the third prototype, introduced in deliverable D4.6 [11] the above subtasks and the Enhanced Interoperability Component are provided as a docker installation with a corresponding Flask application coupled with the utilization of Swagger UI will be implemented in order to provide a

REST application interface following the OpenAPI specification and in order any stakeholder or component to be able to utilize the above-mentioned methods.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

The data store of PolicyCLOUD provides several connectivity methods for all the aforementioned components to integrate. It provides a standard JDBC implementation, a direct API that allows the consumers of the data to connect directly to the storage engine, and various connectors to facilitate its integration with popular analytical frameworks that other components might use, like Spark, Kafka, Flink etc. More information on these interfaces can be found in “D4.6 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 3”. Moreover, it has been containerized and has been used in deployments that rely on the Kubernetes deployment orchestration framework. As a result, it is capable of being deployed on the Cloud Environment of the PolicyCLOUD. The component is under proprietary rights of LXS; however, it is accessible to the members of the consortium and has been uploaded in the private gitlab repository that can be found at:

http://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/lxs-store

To build the image locally, the user needs to execute the following command:

```
docker build -t policy-store
```

Then, having the docker image locally, the container can start issuing the following command:

```
docker run -d -p 1529:1529 -name datastore -env KVPEXTERNAL_IP='datastore!9800' policy-store
```

2.2.8 Data Cleaning

FIGURE 7 - DATA CLEANING

The Data Cleaning component is responsible for undertaking all the processes regarding the data validation and data cleaning of all the incoming heterogeneous data in the PolicyCLOUD platform. Thus, it provides a specific prototype as documented in deliverable D4.6 of the project, which can be utilized by the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components ensuring data accuracy and consistency of the incoming

datasets. As a result, the Data Cleaning component implements all the processes that identify inaccurate or corrupted datasets that may contain inaccurate, incorrect, incomplete, or irrelevant data elements and consequently replace, modify or delete these data elements safeguarding the reliability and appropriateness of the incoming data information.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

In order to successfully implement all the aforementioned actions, the final prototype of the Data Cleaning component consists of three (3) discrete services, namely the ValidationService, the CleaningService, and the VerificationService. Further information regarding these services and the technologies and techniques that are exploited can be found in D4.6. It should be noted that this prototype can work both as a standalone component, and as an integrated part with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components.

The final software prototype of the Data Cleaning is provided in PolicyCLOUD’s GitLab repository and can be found under the URL <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability>

2.2.9 Enhanced Interoperability

FIGURE 8 - ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY

Mapping and creating interoperable data depend on providing semantic and syntactic interoperability across diverse systems, data sources and datasets. To this end, PolicyCLOUD’s Interoperability Component aims to enhance interoperability into PolicyCLOUD project based on data-driven design by the utilization of linked data technologies, and standards-based ontologies and vocabularies, coupled with the use of powerful tasks from the domain of Natural Language Processing (NLP), in order to improve both semantic and syntactic interoperability of data and datasets. To this end, the Enhanced Interoperability Component consists of several methods, and sub-tasks, which are further separated into different layers of the overall proposed pipeline. The initial design of these layers, that integrate Semantic Web technologies with Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies and tasks, includes complete workflows and pipelines for annotating cleaned data, which are being sent into the Enhanced Interoperability Component from the Data Cleaning Component.

Hence, several subtasks and functionalities have been introduced and utilized so far in this component and in the context of its second prototype. More specifically, as also analyzed thoroughly in D4.6 Software Prototype 3, the Enhanced Interoperability mechanism incorporates two main subcomponents, the Linguistic & Semantic Analysis with NLP (1st sub-component) and the Ontology Mapping (2nd sub-component). Furthermore, the abovementioned subcomponents utilize different subtasks from the fields of NLP and Semantic Web, such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), JSON URI annotation, Topic Modeling, and Ontology Mapping.

Moreover, under the scope of the second prototype, introduced in deliverable D4.6 Software Prototype 3 the above subtasks and the Enhanced Interoperability Component are provided as a docker installation with a corresponding Flask application coupled with the utilization of Swagger UI will be implemented in order to provide a REST application interface following the OpenAPI specification and in order any stakeholder or component to be able to utilize the above-mentioned methods.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

Furthermore, software prototype code can be found on the PolicyCLOUD's Gitlab repository, which is accessible to the members of the consortium. As analyzed before, the overall code has been deployed and executed in as a docker image and is accessible under this specific URL <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability>

The full list of the tools and libraries that need to be installed and full configuration and dependencies details about the setup are available to the corresponding README file (<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability/-/blob/master/README.md>).

2.2.10 Analytical Proxy Function

The purpose of this component is to enable the integration of the overall PolicyCLOUD integrated solution with external data analytical frameworks. The policy expert or data scientist interacts with the PolicyCLOUD platform via the *Policy Development Toolkit*. From there, it defines his or her policies that are related with one or more analytical functions, available and discoverable via the DAA component of the data analytics layer. In fact, the developer or provider of an analytical function that desires to make it available through the PolicyCLOUD, needs to register it first, so that it can be discoverable via the PDT. Later, when the end user requests the execution of this function, the latter will be executed inside a virtualized container created and managed by the DAA layer and deployed into the PolicyCLOUD serverless platform. However, there might be the cases where this is not feasible, either due to the architectural design of an external analytical framework (i.e., it might not fit to the serverless paradigm) or due to other restrictions (i.e. mobility of private data).

To solve these issues and in order to allow the integration of the PolicyCLOUD platform with external analytical frameworks, the *Analytical Proxy Function* has been developed. It acts as a proxy between the PolicyCLOUD platform itself and the external data analytical framework. Therefore, it can be registered via the DAA layers so it can be discoverable through the PDT, and upon the end-user invocation, a new virtualized container will be created so that this proxy function can be executed inside the PolicyCLOUD

serverless platform. Then, it will communicate with the external framework via a defined REST API, and will collect the results of this invocation to be later visualized in the PDT.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

This component is under MIT license and its source code is open. The source code can be found in the following repository: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/analytical-proxy

Once having the code, the system integrator will need to compile it first. This requires the use of the maven tool. The system integrator needs then to execute the following:

```
mvn clean package
```

At the end of this process, a *big fat jar* (a jar which includes all its dependencies) will be created under the *target* directory. The system integrator would need to place this jar under the *packaged-functions* folder of the DAA component, so that the proxy can be available to the integrated platform.

Once available, then the system integrator can register different external analytical frameworks. For doing that, we would need to execute the following curl command:

```
curl -k -X PUT
https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -
H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{"kind":"java:8","name":"Policy-
Simulator-UX","filename":"analytical-proxy-1.0-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-
dependencies.jar","main":"eu.policycloud.analytical.proxy.AnalyticalProxy"
,"function_conf_parameters":{"proxy_url":"http://epinoetic.org:5000/ap
i/pol","method":"POST"},"function_parameters":[{"id":"a3a56fe8-
a270-4f34-a28e-
2d6ab3c9cb1e","name":"Base_Case","unit":null,"description":"The
base case policy
parameters","valueType":"GENERIC","evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL
"],"inputType":"VARIABLE","required":true,"valueConstraints":[]},
{"id":"cc7c37a6-c54f-4001-818a-
0c8c77239d2f","name":"Alternatives","unit":null,"description":"S
ampling points for
policy","valueType":"GENERIC","evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
"inputType":"VARIABLE","required":true,"valueConstraints":[]},"g
raph":["HEATMAPTABLECHART"],"policydomain":["AGRIFOOD"],"type":"analytic-
analysis","category":"external","description":"It makes use of Politika,
an external framework","biasDoc":"For the bias analysis please refer to
the external framework of Politika","tradeoffsDoc":"For the tradeoffs
explanation please refer to the external framework of Politika"}'
```

More information regarding the meaning of each of the variables inside the JSON body of this PUT request can be found at the relevant D4.3 and D4.6 deliverables.

2.3 Policy Development Toolkit

FIGURE 9 - POLICY DEVELOPMENT TOOLKIT (PDT)

As a web application, PDT front-end accepts http/https requests from the policymakers - end users to evaluate policies by the execution of analytics tools which calculate the KPIs related with the policies. Web sockets are employed from the PDT-backend for the User notification regarding the status of the submitted jobs.

PDT frontend consumes most of the REST API exposed by the PDT-backend and the Analytics Tools. In addition, it consumes the Authentication API for the User authentication process. The results from the analytics tools are visualized by the Data Visualization component.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

The PDT-front end is being served by the NGINX web server, which is dockerised along with the PDT frontend code.

The installation process and configuration details about the basic setup are available into the README file (<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/kostas/pdt/-/blob/master/README.md>).

The PDT source code (<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/kostas/pdt/-/tree/master>) collectively hosts the PDT Frontend and the Visualization component, the PME (Policy Model Editor) and the IM (Incentive Managements components). The source directory also includes the relevant Dockerfile and docker-compose.yml files for the dockerised building. In order to speed-up the merging process of the source contributions from the components' developers, the dockerised compilation and the deployment of the app with the web server into the RICAS-BARI VM, a bash script has been put in place to automate the procedure. The compilation script as well as the NGINX web configuration files are in the OwnCloud repository:

[<https://newrepository.atosresearch.eu/index.php/apps/files/?dir=/PolicyCLOUD/04%20WPs/05%20WP5-%20Cross-sector%20Policy%20Lifecycle%20Mngmt/PDT/Config&fileid=1203713>]

The adoption of the SSL protocol for the secure https connections, along with the SSL server Certification has been installed following the documentation from Let’s Encrypt (1) [<https://letsencrypt.org>] The NGINX web configuration file also includes the necessary handling of the ssl_certificate.

Finally, regarding the PDT-backend, the source code is open and can be found at the following link:

http://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/pdt-backend

2.4 Data Visualization

FIGURE 10 - DATA VISUALIZATION

During the second year of the project, the visualization component has been integrated completely inside the PDT, although not all charts can yet be accessed through the PDT real flow. The visualization component can be used to plot the results of the different analytics defined in the project, as the final step of the PDT defined flow.

For demo purposes, some visualization examples, with those charts not accessible through the PDT normal flow, have been created for each pilot in order to show how the results of the gathered data in the platform will be displayed at the end of the process. They can be accessed through the PDT URL, but with a specific URL termination. Most of these examples has been created with real data and JSON structure, agreed with WP4, in order to have them exactly as they will be shown, when the integration is completely finalized.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

As the visualization component has been integrated inside the PDT the full source code has been upload into the PDT code repository available here: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/kostas/pdt>

2.5 Authentication & Data Governance Model

FIGURE 11 - DATA GOVERNANCE MODEL

The Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC) component is responsible for intercepting an access request and evaluate it based on the currently implemented policies and user attributes. The component will generate an ALLOW or PERMIT verdict, based on the aforementioned factors. The user attributes required for the evaluation are retrieved in a safe way via a Keycloak server that acts both as an Attribute Provider and a User Authenticator.

The first version of the component consisted of the ABAC Server, the ABAC Client Filter and the connected Keycloak server instance. The Keycloak Server can be configured to host multiple client applications with the same user base, in order to accommodate multiple pilots operating simultaneously. The continued development of the platform created the need to include a new component in this version, the ABAC Proxy, which helps integrate ABAC with non-Java applications.

The installation process for all three of the subcomponents, as well as instructions for their connection can be found in greater detail at deliverable “D3.7 Cloud Infrastructure Incentives Management and Data Governance: Software Prototype 3” [5].

In the first version, a web client app utilizing the component was accessible at policycloud.eu.projects.net while the Keycloak server is available at policycloud-auth.eu.projects.net. In the current version, the component has been integrated with the PDT and thus the user is prompted to first login to Keycloak in order to gain access to it, as shown on Figure 12.

FIGURE 12 - KEYCLOAK LOGIN

After a successful login, the ABAC Engine evaluates the request and permits access to the PDT or denies it accordingly. Keycloak also acts as an attribute provider for the user attributes in the profile page of the PDT. Another useful feature implemented is EGI Check-In, as also shown on the right-hand side of Figure 12. This provides an alternate login option to the platform, via academic or social credentials, as shown on Figure 13.

FIGURE 13 - EGI CHECK-IN

This feature allows users that are not already registered in the PolicyCLOUD ecosystem have access to its tools, thus increasing even further the potential user base of the project.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

The source code of the components is available to https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/oikonomou/abac_proxy.git.

2.6 Data Marketplace

FIGURE 14 - DATA MARKETPLACE

The Data Marketplace is a standalone platform of the PolicyCLOUD that aims to create a community of users who will be able, through this platform, to provide and share various ready-to-use solutions/tools to various subjects and fields of use, related to the areas of interest of the PolicyCLOUD. The assets that may derive from the separate procedures and mechanisms that are implemented in the PolicyCLOUD platform are going to be exploited by offering them to the Data Marketplace’s users who may be either project’s partners or interested third parties. To achieve such goals, an integrated and public web-based environment has been developed for the Data Marketplace that introduces several APIs to manage the requirements and the functionalities of the Data Marketplace. In more technical details, the Marketplace has been structured and developed having two core components, the back-end that contains in a structured way the information and stores the assets offered by the Marketplace, and the front-end that presents to the users the offered contents, allowing them to interact with the platform in an easier way, using its web-based user interface.

All this information (i.e., objectives, architecture, technical details and interfaces of the Data Marketplace are furtherly described in the Data Marketplace’s relevant deliverables – D7.11 and D7.12.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

FIGURE 15 - POLICYCLOUD MARKETPLACE PORTAL

The page of Data Marketplace’s component is available through the website <https://marketplace.policycloud.eu/>.

2.7 Incentives Management

FIGURE 16 - INCENTIVES MANAGEMENT

During the third year of the project, the final version of the incentives management tool has been developed. In order to integrate this component into the project infrastructure, this component has been divided in two parts. The Frontend part, that provides the GUI, has been integrated inside the PDT, and the Backend part that exposes APIs to interact with the component database.

SOURCE CODE AND INTEGRATION DETAILS

As the frontend part of incentives management component has been integrated inside the PDT, the full source code of this component has been uploaded into the PDT code repository available here: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/kostas/pdt>

The backend part of the incentives management component has his own git repository here https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/ana.pontual/incentivesmanagement_be

The backend is being served with a NGINX web server and a Flask server (Python). The component has been dockerized to facilitate the deployment.

3 Source code management

The development of such a large European Project can be a very complex task. To ensure code quality and to test the developed components (designed and implemented by the partners) integration guidelines and a centralized platform are vital. The integration guidelines are the necessary coding principles that should be followed as well as the steps that a developer should followed in order to be aligned with the ethical framework that is presented to the project.

ANALYTICS

The project has 29 subprojects (from 13 that had during the first year and 25 that had during the second period)

Total projects & groups

FIGURE 17 - TOTAL PROJECTS & GROUPS

We have 24 members to the platform (compared to 18 during the first year and 23 during the second period)

Total users

FIGURE 18 - TOTAL USERS

The project has several pipelines – that are the top-level component of continuous integration, delivery, and deployment- in order to define each job (that could be compile or test code) or develop stages which define when to run these jobs. We keep track of all pipelines (even the deprecated) for logging purposes.

FIGURE 19 - PIPELINES

during the final year of the project the main goal was to test the interoperability of the components and simplify the interconnections between them. The figure below depicts the trend of that task and the almost stable number of issues that we face during the last period of the project.

FIGURE 20 - ISSUES & MERGE REQUESTS

All the details and information about the statistics and the coda are available to the GitLAB repository server (<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/>).

4 Cloud Environment

The PolicyCLOUD cloud-based infrastructure is composed of IaaS-type cloud resources provided by EGI. From a technical perspective these resources are provided by RECAS-BARI [4] and IISAS FedCloud [14], two OpenStack cloud providers selected from the EGI Federation [15] via an open call. They empower users with an API-based service to enable the management of Virtual Machines and associated Block Storage, and the connectivity of the Virtual Machines among themselves and third-party resources. In the context of the PolicyCLOUD project the cloud provider is offering:

- 272 vCPU cores, 672 GB of RAM, 4TB of block storage and 50-100GB of object storage, and
- a PaaS orchestrator [16], with no additional costs, to facilitate the deployment and the operation of Kubernetes clusters where members of the project can deploy services and run pilots.

For more details, please refer to the Service Level Agreement between PolicyCLOUD and EGI [12].

The EGI Federated Cloud is hosting the following PolicyCLOUD services:

- Data Marketplace
- Interim Repository
- Cloud Gateways and APIs
- Keycloak Server
- OpenWhisk cluster
- Policy Development Toolkit (with the associated front-end and back-end components)
- Incentive Management component

5 Conclusion

The outcomes of this deliverable provided valuable input to the integration orchestration. All these details are related to the design of the overall architecture of the platform and PolicyCLOUD environment.

The main scope is to depict the exact state of each component via a brief description of it, a figure which positions the component into the architecture and technical details of the source code and repository.

As this is the final version of this deliverable we included comparison details and metrics about the code usage and services.

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